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Research Article

Blasphemous Speech Against Islam in Religious Debate Groups on Facebook: A Forensic Linguistics Study

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ABSTRACT

Social media today functions not only as a platform for sharing information but also as a space for debates, including those on religion. One emerging phenomenon is the presence of blasphemous speech against Islam, particularly in online debates between Muslim and Christian users on Facebook. This study aims to identify forms of blasphemy against Islam in the Islam versus Christianity debate groups. This research uses a descriptive qualitative approach. The data consists of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences suspected of containing blasphemous speech against Islam, taken from nine posts in Facebook debate groups during October–November 2023. Data were collected through screenshots and analyzed using theories of meaning analysis, implicature, and stylistics. The analysis revealed that the nine posts contained elements of blasphemy against Islam, including: (a) insults toward God and Islamic symbols; (b) blasphemy against Islamic teachings and the Qur'an; and (c) negative stereotyping of Islam as a religion and social identity. These findings illustrate how vulnerable social media is to the spread of hate speech and blasphemy. Based on the analysis, netizens who commit blasphemous speech may be subject to sanctions in the form of imprisonment and/or fines, in accordance with applicable Indonesian regulations. This study highlights the urgent need for linguistic awareness and ethical communication on social media, especially in religious discourse. It is expected to serve as a reminder for users to express their opinions responsibly to avoid legal consequences and social harm.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Social media has grown into a significant social phenomenon, with the number of users increasing every year. Numerous social media platforms have been created and utilized by society, one of which is Facebook. Facebook has become the largest social media platform, boasting 3 billion active users (Annur, 2023). This growth has significantly impacted the way people communicate and interact. Today, social media is no longer merely a tool for building social relationships but also serves as a source of information, entertainment, and a forum for discussion (Harahap & Adeni, 2020; Indriani & Prasanti, 2020; Supratman, 2018). The diverse functions of social media have created a complex and dynamic space for interaction and the exchange of ideas (Ginting *et al.*, 2024).

With easy access to social media, individuals can freely express their opinions (Jayananda *et al.*, 2021; Kamba *et al.*, 2024). Posts, comments, and various other forms of digital interaction allow netizens to actively participate in sharing ideas, views, or aspirations. Along with this development, the phenomenon of forming debate groups on social media has emerged. These groups serve as a platform for individuals with shared interests and perspectives to discuss various issues, including sensitive topics such as religion. One notable example of such groups on Facebook is the Islam versus Christianity religious debate group. The Islam versus Christianity debate group serves as an interreligious dialogue space, enabling representatives from both faiths to speak and listen to each other. This can foster better understanding between the Islamic and Christian communities. These Facebook debate groups are established to discuss Islamic and Christian teachings rationally and logically, ultimately aiming to evaluate the correctness of these teachings. Through discussion, group members can compare the fundamental beliefs and teachings of Islam and Christianity. Unfortunately, some netizens in these groups do not adhere to the rules set by the group administrators. Certain individuals express their opinions without using wise and thoughtful language. This lack of prudence in language use leads to discussions toward negative outcomes, such as insulting, harassing, or blaspheming religion. Such behavior can result in tension, conflict, and even harm to specific individuals or groups (Lokananta & Herlina, 2018).

This study aims to uncover suspected blasphemous speech within the Islam versus Christianity debate group on Facebook using a forensic linguistics approach. Forensic linguistics is used to determine whether a person's statement can be proven to be blasphemous. The focus of this research is to analyze suspected blasphemous statements directed at Islam. This focus was chosen to allow for a more in-depth examination of blasphemous speech against Islam and to identify patterns of such speech.

Conversely, this study does not aim to discredit Christian teachings or its followers, as its primary goal is to contribute to the field of forensic linguistics. Additionally, most members of the debate group use fake accounts, so individuals responsible for blasphemous speech can be referred to as perpetrators rather than representatives of any particular religious group. Furthermore, the objectives of this research are twofold: (1) to examine the forms of speech that constitute an insult to Islam;

and (2) to explain the legal consequences of such insulting speech according to the laws in effect in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Forensic linguistics is an interdisciplinary subfield of linguistics that examines the relationship between language, law, and criminal acts (Ahmed, 2021; Ali, 2020; Kuntarto, 2021). Furthermore, Panggabean (2022) and Perkins (2021) explain that forensic linguistics is a branch of applied linguistics that integrates linguistic theories into language-related incidents involved in legal processes, including legal products, courtroom interactions, and interpersonal interactions resulting in legal implications. This field plays a crucial role in supporting law enforcement and crime investigations.

Forensic linguistics applies principles discovered and developed in various branches of linguistic studies for forensic purposes (Alduais *et al.*, 2023; Aziz, 2021). Therefore, to uncover suspected blasphemous speech against Islam by netizens in the Islam versus Christianity debate group on Facebook, linguistic analysis is required to understand the meaning and intent behind the speech. This analysis includes semantic analysis, implicature analysis, and stylistic analysis.

Chaer (2014) states that language encompasses various types of meaning, including lexical, grammatical, and contextual meanings. Lexical meaning refers to the inherent meaning of a word (lexeme) without any context or can be described as its literal meaning (Siahaan *et al.*, 2022). Grammatical meaning arises when a word undergoes grammatical processes such as affixation, reduplication, composition, or sentence formation (Setiowati *et al.*, 2022). Contextual meaning is determined by considering the context in which the word is used (Setyawan, 2022). In other words, a word can only be accurately understood when its context is taken into account.

Regarding implicature analysis, Sari *et al.* (2020) explain that implicature refers to the hidden meaning behind a speaker's or listener's utterance. Othman & Salih (2021); Sbisà, (2021); and Yuliantoro (2020) describes implicature as an additional meaning or explanation that is not explicitly stated in a statement or utterance. In other words, implicature provides a deeper understanding of what is not directly said. It helps interpret statements or utterances with greater depth and nuance.

Furthermore, stylistics is a sub-discipline of linguistics that studies language style. Stylistics relates to the style of language used in a text created by an author, whether in literary or non-literary works (Kuntarto, 2021; Manqoush & Al-Wadhaf, 2021; Muhassin, 2017). This field is used to analyze netizen posts that employ specific language styles, enabling a comprehensive understanding of such posts.

Previous studies relevant to this research have been conducted by several researchers. First, Rahman (2019) studied types of taboo words on social media that potentially violate the law. The study found that taboo words used on social media include (1) obscene words, (2) vulgar language, and (3) name-calling and insults. These taboo words have the potential to violate Article 27 paragraph (3) and Article 45 paragraph (1) of the Indonesian Law No. 11 of 2008 on Electronic Information and Transactions (ITE Law) as well as Articles 310 paragraph (1)

and 311 paragraph (1) of the Indonesian Penal Code concerning defamation. Second, Permatasari & Subyantoro (2020) examined forms of hate speech by Ahmad Dhani Prasetyo (ADP) on Facebook. The study revealed that ADP was proven to have committed hate speech in the form of provocation, incitement, insults, defamation, slander, and the dissemination of false information.

Third, Fadhlorrohman (2021) investigated offensive speech suspected as a criminal act of religious defamation on Twitter. The study found that several Twitter users engaged in assertive, directive, expressive, commissive, and declarative speech acts containing blasphemy against Islam. Fourth, Syahid *et al.* (2022) researched illocutionary acts of cyberbullying involving religious blasphemy on social media carried out by Joseph Paul Zhang and M. Kece. The study found that the defendants performed three types of illocutionary acts: expressive acts indicating hate speech, directive acts indicating insults and blasphemy, and assertive acts indicating falsehoods. Cyberbullying involving religious blasphemy on social media was characterized by the use of harsh mockery, insults, blasphemy against religious communities, God, prophets, holy scriptures, and other religious symbols.

Based on the literature review above, the similarities and differences between this research and previous studies can be identified. The similarity lies in focusing on the analysis of religious blasphemy on social media using forensic linguistics. The difference, however, lies in the research object. This study examines religious blasphemy within a religious debate group on Facebook, which has not been previously studied. This research brings novelty by focusing on religious debate groups on Facebook, providing a more specific understanding of how religious blasphemy emerges in that context. Additionally, this study contributes further insights into forensic linguistics in the context of religious blasphemy on social media.

From the literature review, it is also evident that studies on linguistic crimes on social media have been widely conducted. This highlights the importance of forensic linguistic research in today's digital era to raise awareness among netizens and encourage them to be wise in expressing their opinions on social media.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study is categorized as descriptive qualitative research. The research data consist of words, phrases, clauses, and sentences

suspected of containing speech acts that insult Islam. The data source comprises posts made by netizens in Facebook groups debating Islam versus Christianity during the period of October to November 2023. Nine posts were purposively selected based on three main criteria: (1) content that explicitly or implicitly targets Islamic symbols (such as Allah, the Qur'an, or Prophet Muhammad PBUH); (2) the use of provocative, offensive, or derogatory language; and (3) reactions or comments from other users indicating controversy or disagreement with the post.

Data were collected by taking screenshots of the selected posts. These screenshots were then transcribed into written text. The original texts in Indonesian were subsequently translated into English for broader academic analysis and documentation.

This study follows ethical principles in qualitative research, particularly in the use of online data. Although the data were obtained from publicly accessible Facebook groups, ethical considerations were applied to protect the rights and privacy of the individuals involved. All usernames, profile information, and any identifiable personal details were anonymized to prevent the identification of the netizens. The use of anonymization reflects respect for human rights and adheres to the principle of presumption of innocence. In addition, the data were analyzed solely for academic purposes, without any intention to stigmatize, judge, or harm individuals or religious communities. Comments from other netizens were considered only to understand the context of controversy and public reaction, not to evaluate or target specific individuals.

Data analysis was carried out using three linguistic approaches: (1) meaning analysis, to examine explicit and implicit messages in the text; (2) implicature analysis, to uncover implied intentions behind the utterances; and (3) stylistic analysis, to identify language choices, styles, and rhetorical effects used in the posts. These analyses were then connected to forensic linguistic studies to assess whether the language used constitutes religious blasphemy from both linguistic and legal perspectives. Upon completion of the analysis, the findings were presented in the form of examples of blasphemous statements, followed by a summary of recurring patterns found in the speech acts deemed blasphemous against Islam.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

After conducting an in-depth analysis, nine posts from netizens in the Islam versus Christianity debate group on Facebook were identified as allegedly defaming Islam.

Table 1. List of blasphemous statements against Islam

Transcription of the Statement in Indonesian (Original Text)	Transcription of the Statement in English (Translated Text)
Data 1	
Teriakan Allahuakbar menandakan Muslim telah kerasukan ISLAM identik dengan setan. ...	The shout of Allahu Akbar signifies that muslims are possessed. ISLAM is identical to satan.
Hampir semua muslim yang brutal dan kesetanan, selalu meneriakkan kata-kata "ALLAHU AKBAR". Ini artinya, ALLAH SWT identik dengan hal-hal yang merusak, yang brutal, tidak rasional dan jahat. Bila ALLAH SWT lebih condong pada hal-hal yang jahat, jadi inilah bukti nyata kita kalau ALLAH SWT adalah nama diri dari SETAN.	... Almost all brutal and demon-possessed muslims always shout the words 'ALLAHU AKBAR'. This means that ALLAH SWT is associated with destructive, brutal, irrational, and evil things. If ALLAH SWT tends more toward evil, then this is concrete proof that ALLAH SWT is the proper name of SATAN.

...	...
Secara rasional, ayat-ayat Alquran memang kata-kata karangan Muhammad. Tapi secara metafisik, ayat-ayat Alquran berasal dari setan yang diucapkan lewat perantaraan bibir Muhammad. Kembali ke masalah "Allahuakbar".	Rationally, the verses of the Quran are indeed the writings of Muhammad. But metaphysically, the Quranic verses come from satan, spoken through Muhammad's lips. Back to the matter of 'Allahu Akbar'.
...	...
Teriakan Allahuakbar adalah semacam stimulan untuk merangsang gairah kemarahan, untuk menghilangkan kesadaran diri dan nurani.	The shout of Allahu Akbar is a kind of stimulant to provoke anger, to eliminate self-awareness and conscience.
...	...
Ya, inilah bukti, kalau ISLAM adalah penyembah setan.	Yes, this is proof that ISLAM worships satan.

Data 2

Malam ini agama Arab Saudi sudah pasti pesta seks, kan malam Jumat	Tonight, the religion of Saudi Arabia is surely having a sex party, right? It's Thursday night.
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Data 3

AL-QUR'AN hanya firman Palsu berisi dongeng-dongeng:	THE QUR'AN is merely a collection of false statements filled with fables:
...	...
i. DONGENG YAKJUI DAN MAKJUI dijiplak dari kitab Sermon & Homily Mar Jacob Serug, (abad-6 M).	i. THE FABLE OF GOG AND MAGOG Plagiarized from the Sermon & Homily of Mar Jacob Serug (6th century AD).
ii. DONGENG ISRA MIRAJ dicipta memakai cerita rakyat dalam Kitab Testament of Abraham dan Mishkatul Masabih.	ii. THE FABLE OF ISRA MI'RAJ Created using folklore found in the Testament of Abraham and Mishkatul Masabih.
iii. DONGENG SIDRATUL MUNTAHA dicipta memakai cerita rakyat dalam kitab Enoch dan Testament of Abraham (abad-1 SM)	iii. THE FABLE OF SIDRATUL MUNTAHA Created using folklore from the Book of Enoch and the Testament of Abraham (1st century BC).
iv. DONGENG 7 LAPISAN LANGIT dijiplak dari Kitab Talmud Yahudi (abad-3 M) dan Midrash Genesis Rabbah (abad-6 M)	iv. THE FABLE OF THE SEVEN HEAVENS Plagiarized from the Jewish Talmud (3rd century AD) and Midrash Genesis Rabbah (6th century AD).
v. DONGENG NERAKA PENUH AIR MENDIDIH, NANAH DAN WANITA DIGANTUNG DENGAN KEDUA BUAH DADA MEREKA dijiplak dari kitab apocryp Peter (The Akhmim Fragment) dan Kitab Zorasther: Arda Viraf.	v. THE FABLE OF HELL WITH BOILING WATER, PUS, AND WOMEN HUNG BY THEIR BREASTS Plagiarized from the Apocryphal Gospel of Peter (The Akhmim Fragment) and the Zoroastrian Arda Viraf.
vi. DONGENG HARTA KARUN dijiplak dari Tract Sanhedrin, kitab Yahudi.	vi. THE FABLE OF TREASURES Plagiarized from the Jewish Tractate Sanhedrin.
vii. DONGENG BUKIT YANG TERANGKAT MENAUNGI ORANG ISRAEL dijiplak dari kitab apocryp Yahudi yang bernama Tract 'Abodah Zarah.	vii. THE FABLE OF A MOUNTAIN SUSPENDED OVER THE PEOPLE OF ISRAEL Plagiarized from the Jewish apocryphal text Tractate 'Abodah Zarah.
viii. DONGENG PEMUDA PEMUDA YANG TERTIDUR DALAM GUA dijiplak dari kisah dalam kitab apocryp Kristen "The Seven Sleeper."	viii. THE FABLE OF YOUTHS SLEEPING IN A CAVE Plagiarized from the Christian apocryphal story of The Seven Sleepers.

Data 4

Assalamualaikum. Para kadrin-kadrin, para ahli pemegang kunci surga, dan para ahli agama dongeng yang dibanggakan Allah Swt. Ane cuma menyampaikan ya. Kalau memang Al-Qur'an itu suci, setan, iblis, dan jin tidak akan mampu mendengarkan Qur'an itu. Jadi, kalau dilihat Al-Qur'an itu seperti mantra-mantra gaib ya yang diucapkan oleh ustad-ustad dan dukun-dukun untuk memanggil setan dan jin. Bagi para kadrin-kadrin atau ahli agama dongeng coba jelaskan dong.	Assalamualaikum. To all the kadrin-kadrin, the experts holding the keys to heaven, and the experts of fairy tale religion proudly cherished by Allah Swt. I'm just here to share something. If the Qur'an is truly holy, then demons, devils, and jinn would not be able to hear it. So, if you look at it, the Qur'an seems like magical incantations recited by ustad and shamans to summon demons and jinn. To all the kadrin-kadrin or experts of fairy tale religion, could you please explain?
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Data 5

Jin atau setan dapat berubah wujud dan bentuk rupa. Seperti yang terjadi kepada Muhammad yang saat itu berada di dalam gua di mana jin al-abyad yang berwujud atau menjelma sebagai malaikat, memberikan ayat-ayat setan kepada Muhammad untuk disatukan ke dalam Alquran. Kata “Jangan Banyak Bertanya, Tapi Hafalkan saja” kata ini sama hal nya seperti Jin al-abyad (wujud malaikat Jibril) menyuruh Muhammad “banyak bertanya, tapi bacalah”.

Jadi, Alquran itu berasal dari jin atau setan.

Yang mengajarkan kesesatan seperti kotoran, membunuh, berzina, berpoligami, dll untuk menjaminkan menuju surga. Tapi, itu semuanya “hoax”, itu jalan menuju neraka.

Namanya iblis, jin atau setan tidak mengajarkan kebenaran, tapi dia meraka paling benar dan mulia. Selalu menolak kebenaran dan menyangkal kebaikan.

Salam waras dan berpikir yang sehat.

Jinns or devils can change their forms and appearances. For instance, what happened to Muhammad when he was in the cave, where Jin Al-Abyad, taking the form of an angel, delivered satanic verses to Muhammad to be included in the Quran. The phrase ‘Do not ask too many questions, just memorize it’ is similar to how Jin Al-Abyad (in the form of Angel Gabriel) instructed Muhammad to ‘ask many questions, but read it’.

Therefore, the Quran comes from jinns or devils.

It teaches misguidance, such as filth, murder, adultery, polygamy, etc., as a guarantee for entering paradise. But it is all a ‘hoax’—it is the path to hell.

The nature of devils, jinns, or demons is that they never teach the truth. Instead, they claim to be the most truthful and noble. They always reject the truth and deny goodness.

Greetings to sanity and healthy thinking.

Data 6

Islam MEMUSUHI Kristen = bentrok

Islam MEMUSUHI Hindu = bentrok

Islam MEMUSUHI Budha = bentrok

Islam MEMUSUHI Aliran Kepercayaan = bentrok

Hindu + Budha = Damai

Hindu + aliran kepercayaan = Damai

Budha + aliran kepercayaan = Damai

Kristen + Hindu = Damai

Kristen + Budha = Damai

Kristen + Aliran kepercayaan = Damai

Umiss agama klian terbuat dari apa sih? Kok musuh dan bentrok dengan semua agama lain?

Islam ENEMIES Christianity = conflict

Islam ENEMIES Hinduism = conflict

Islam ENEMIES Buddhism = conflict

Islam ENEMIES Indigenous Beliefs = conflict

Hinduism + Buddhism = Peace

Hinduism + Indigenous Beliefs = Peace

Buddhism + Indigenous Beliefs = Peace

Christianity + Hinduism = Peace

Christianity + Buddhism = Peace

Christianity + Indigenous Beliefs = Peace

What is your religion made of? Why does it become enemies and conflict with all other religions?

Data 7

Negara-negara mayoritas Islam selalu kalah.

Ekonomi, selalu miskin.

Perang, pasti kalah.

Politik, sering dikadalin.

Sosial, minder.

Budaya, mudah dipengaruhi

SDM, paling bodoh.....

Ngakunya agama yang diridhoi, kok nasibnya apes melulu?

Uh, nasib ya nasib.

Majority-muslim countries always lose.

Economically, always poor.

In wars, always defeated.

Politically, often tricked.

Socially, insecure.

Culturally, easily influenced.

Human resources, the dumbest...

Claiming to be the religion favored by God, yet their fate is always miserable?

Oh, fate is fate.

Data 8

Menurut ustad somad, yang disalib itu Yudas

Menurut ustad waloni, yang disalib itu Barabas

Menurut ustad kainama, yang disalib itu Yokohanana

Ngakak banget islam

Mereka tidak tahu pasti siapa yang disalib

Islam raja ngibul

According to Ustad Somad, the one who was crucified was Judas.

According to Ustad Waloni, the one who was crucified was Barabbas.

According to Ustad Kainama, the one who was crucified was Yokohanana.

So funny, Islam.

They do not even know who was crucified.

Islam, king of lies.

Data 9

Logikanya saja ya, Islam muncul 600 SM setelah adanya kekristenan dan dengan tanpa malu, kadrun-kadrun mencuri beberapa ayat Alkitab untuk menjadi dalil Al-Qur'annya terutama tentang pokok Yesus Kristus diubah menjadi Nabi Isa dengan cara memalsukannya.

Si bungsu memang lucu sekali ya

Sampai Yesus pun mau di-Islam-kan

Logically speaking, Islam emerged 600 years after Christianity, and shamelessly, kadrun-kadrun stole several verses from the Bible to serve as arguments in the Qur'an, especially regarding the figure of Jesus Christ, who was turned into Prophet Isa by falsifying him.

The youngest child is really funny, huh?

Even Jesus is being 'Islamized'

The nine data presented in the results section reveal various forms of utterances that explicitly and implicitly target Islamic teachings, symbols, and identity. To further understand the nature and implications of these utterances, this discussion is divided into two main parts. The first part examines the forms of speech acts that constitute insults to Islam based on linguistic features. The second part discusses the legal consequences of such speech under the laws currently in effect in Indonesia. These analyses use meaning analysis, implicature analysis, and stylistic analysis, as well as references to relevant legal instruments to determine whether the utterances fulfill the criteria of religious blasphemy both linguistically and legally.

4.1. Forms of speech acts that constitute insults to Islam

This section analyzes the linguistic features found in the nine utterances to determine whether they can be categorized as religious blasphemy. By applying meaning analysis, implicature analysis, and stylistic analysis, this section identifies how language is used to express hostility, mockery, or degradation toward Islamic teachings, sacred texts, or religious symbols. The utterances are grouped into three main categories based on their targets: (a) insults toward God and Islamic symbols; (b) blasphemy against Islamic teachings and the Qur'an; and (c) negative stereotyping of Islam as a religion and social identity. The first form of blasphemous speech against Islam can be seen in data 1. In data 1, a Facebook user named Man xxx made a post containing several statements discussing Islam, muslims, and the phrase takbir (Allahu Akbar). The post includes blasphemous content against Islam, analyzed as follows.

First, Man xxx makes statements insulting Islam by associating the phrase "Allahu Akbar" with negative actions or behaviors. This is evident in the following sentences: (1) Teriakan Allahu Akbar menandakan muslim telah kerasukan (The shout of Allahu Akbar signifies that muslims are possessed); (2) Hampir semua muslim yang brutal dan kesetanan, selalu meneriakkan kata-kata "Allahu Akbar" (Almost all brutal and demon-possessed muslims always shout the words 'Allahu Akbar') and (3) Teriakan Allahu Akbar adalah semacam stimulan untuk merangsang gairah kemarahan, untuk menghilangkan kesadaran diri dan nurani (The shout of Allahu Akbar is a kind of stimulant to provoke anger, to eliminate self-awareness and conscience).

The phrase "Allahu Akbar" is a form of takbir, meaning "Allah is the Greatest", as defined by the Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI). The term kerasukan (possessed) refers to being "under the influence of an evil spirit". Thus, statement (1) implies that a muslim shouting "Allahu Akbar" (which is meant to glorify Allah SWT) is a sign of being possessed by an evil spirit.

Therefore, Man xxx indirectly associates the greatness of Allah SWT with an evil spirit. Similarly, statements (2) and (3) contain derogatory elements. The word brutal in statement (2) means "cruel" and kesetanan (demon-possessed) means "possessed by a demon or evil spirit", resulting in a lack of self-control. Thus, statement (2) implies that most cruel and demon-possessed muslims always shout "Allahu Akbar". In other words, "Allahu Akbar" becomes a driving force for muslims when committing cruelty or acting irrationally.

Second, Man xxx makes statements insulting Islam by equating it with satan. This is evident in the following sentences: (4) Islam identik dengan setan (Islam is identical to satan); and (5) Ya, inilah bukti, kalau Islam adalah penyembah setan (Yes, this is proof that ISLAM worships satan). Statement (4) employs a simile by equating Islam with satan using the phrase "identical to". According to the Indonesian Dictionary, setan (satan) means "an evil spirit that tempts humans to commit sin". Thus, the statement suggests that Islam shares similarities with evil spirits, implying that Islam teaches its followers to commit evil. Statement (5) uses metaphorical language to convey the same intent, equating Islam with worshiping satan.

Third, Man xxx makes statements insulting Allah SWT. This is evident in the following sentences: (6) Ini artinya, Allah Swt. identik dengan hal-hal yang merusak, yang brutal, tidak rasional, dan jahat (This means that Allah SWT is associated with destructive, brutal, irrational, and evil things); (7) Bila Allah Swt. lebih condong pada hal-hal yang jahat, jadi inilah bukti nyata kita kalau Allah Swt. adalah nama diri dari setan (If Allah SWT tends more toward evil, then this is concrete proof that Allah SWT is the proper name of satan); and (8) Ayat-ayat Al-Qur'an berasal dari setan yang diucapkan lewat perantaraan bibir Muhammad (The verses of the Quran come from satan, spoken through Muhammad's lips). Statement (6) employs a simile, associating Allah SWT with negative traits such as destructiveness, brutality, irrationality, and evil. In statement (7), a metaphor is used to equate Allah SWT with an evil spirit (satan). Additionally, in statement (8), Man xxx claims that the Quranic verses originate from satan. The Quran is the holy book of muslims, containing the words of Allah SWT. Thus, statement (8) implies that the Quran, as the word of Allah, is derived from satan, equating Allah's words with those of satan. The second form of blasphemous speech against Islam can be seen in data 2-5. In data 2, the owner of a Facebook account named Pec xxx posted a statement suggesting that on the night of his post, which was Thursday night, muslims were engaging in a sex party. The phrase pesta sex (sex party) consists of two words: pesta (party) and seks (sex). According to the dictionary, party means "a celebration or gathering involving food and

drink for enjoyment". It refers to an activity where several people gather in one place for amusement. Meanwhile, sex means "matters related to sexual organs, such as intercourse or copulation". Therefore, sex party can be interpreted as "a gathering of several people for a celebration involving sexual intercourse for enjoyment". A sex party inherently refers to an act of fornication, as it is not possible for legitimate married couples to engage in sexual activities openly and collectively with other married couples in the same place.

Based on the explanation above, it can be understood that Pec xxx's statement degraded Islam by equating it with a liberal Western lifestyle. In Western culture, sex parties are considered normal activities, whereas in Islam, they are acts of fornication that are strictly prohibited. Islam upholds the dignity and honor of individuals, and therefore forbids fornication. It is true that Islam encourages legitimate married couples to engage in intimacy on Thursday nights. However, this is meant to be done privately and not openly or collectively as in the context of Western-style sex parties.

In data 3, the Facebook user named Sog xxx made a post explaining their perspective on the Qur'an. They stated in the sentence, Al-Qur'an hanya firman palsu berisi dongeng-dongeng (The Qur'an is merely a collection of false statements filled with fables). This statement constitutes blasphemy against Islam, as evidenced by the use of the phrases "false statements" and the word "fables". The phrase firman palsu (false statements) is composed of two words. According to the dictionary, the word firman (statements) means "the word of God", while palsu (false) means "not authentic, invalid, or an imitation". Therefore, the phrase "false statements" can be interpreted as claiming that the word of God (Allah Swt.) is invalid or an imitation of something else. The word dongeng-dongeng (fables) comes from the root word "fable", which means "a story that did not actually happen, especially about strange or illogical events from the past, or false statements". The plural form "fables" implies that, according to Sog xxx, the Qur'an contains many such fabricated stories.

Based on the explanation above, the meaning of Soga's first sentence is that the Qur'an is the word of God (Allah Swt.) that is a mere imitation of other sources and contains numerous fabricated or false stories. Furthermore, Sog xxx elaborates in subsequent sentences about eight alleged "fables" in the Qur'an: the stories of Gog and Magog, Isra Mi'raj, Sidratul Muntaha, the seven heavens, hell, treasures, a mountain suspended over the people of Israel, and youths sleeping in a cave. These statements indicate that Sog xxx has blasphemed Islam by claiming that the Qur'an is filled with fabricated stories. However, in many verses of the Qur'an, Allah Swt. asserts that the Qur'an is truly the word of Allah Swt. and challenges anyone who doubts it to produce verses that can match its greatness, as mentioned in Surah Al-Isra: 88, Hud: 13-14, Yunus: 38, and Al-Baqarah: 23. This divine challenge indicates that the stories in the Qur'an are not fables but rather divine revelations.

In data 4, the Facebook account owner, Luc xxx, expressed their opinion about the Qur'an in five sentences. In sentence (1), Luc xxx addresses the group members who are Muslims with the words, Para kadrin-kadrin, para ahli pemegang kunci surga, dan para ahli agama dongeng yang dibanggakan Allah Swt (To

all the kadrin-kadrin, the experts holding the keys to heaven, and the experts of fairy tale religion proudly cherished by Allah Swt). In this sentence, Luc xxx refers to Muslims as kadrin, an acronym for kadal gurun (desert lizard), and also refers to them with the phrase "experts of fairy tale religion". This sentence constitutes blasphemy against Islam as it implies that Islam is a "fairy tale religion". According to the dictionary, the word dongeng (fairy tale) means "a story that did not actually happen, especially concerning strange or illogical events from the past". Therefore, the phrase "fairy tale religion" in this sentence implies that Islam is a religion filled with fabricated, false, or fictitious stories.

Another statement containing blasphemy against Islam is found in sentence (4): Jadi, kalau dilihat Al-Qur'an itu seperti mantra-mantra gaib ya yang diucap oleh ustad-ustad dan dukun-dukun untuk memanggil setan dan jin (So, if you look at it, the Qur'an seems like magical incantations recited by ustad and shamans to summon demons and jinn). Sentence (4) employs a simile, marked by the word seems like. In this sentence, Luc xxx equates the Qur'an to magical incantations. The phrase "magical incantations" refers to "a poetic arrangement of words with rhythm or rhyme believed to hold supernatural power, usually recited by shamans or practitioners to counter other supernatural forces". Comparing the Qur'an to magical incantations constitutes blasphemy against Islam because it indirectly equates the Qur'an to human creations rather than divine words from Allah Swt. However, Allah Swt asserts in many verses, such as in Surah Al-Ahqaf: 7-8 and Surah Al-Isra: 88, that the Qur'an is the word of Allah and not a form of magic. Furthermore, the final part of sentence (4) also contains blasphemy against Islam. According to the dictionary, the word setan (demon) means "an evil spirit that always tempts humans to commit wrongdoings", while jin (jinn) means "a supernatural being created from fire". In Islam, jinn are classified into two types: good jinn and evil jinn. In the context of the above sentence, demons are paired with jinn, implying that the jinn in this statement are evil jinn. Thus, Luc xxx's statement suggests that the Qur'an is used to summon evil beings like demons and jinn. Based on this, Luc xxx has blasphemed against Islam by stating that Islam is akin to incantations used to summon malevolent forces.

In data 5, a Facebook user named Luc xxx posted a statement about the Quran. The post contains blasphemy against Islam. This is evident in the sentence: Seperti yang terjadi kepada Muhammad yang saat itu berada di dalam gua di mana Jin Al-Abyad yang berwujud atau menjelma sebagai malaikat, memberikan ayat-ayat setan kepada Muhammad untuk disatukan ke dalam Alquran (For instance, what happened to Muhammad when he was in the cave, where Jin Al-Abyad, taking the form of an angel, delivered satanic verses to Muhammad to be included in the Quran). The essence of this statement is that Jin Al-Abyad gave satanic verses to Muhammad to be incorporated into the Quran. This implies that, according to Luc xxx, the verses in the Quran are satanic. This assertion is baseless and demeaning to Islam.

Another statement that contains blasphemy is: Jadi, Alquran itu berasal dari jin atau setan (Therefore, the Quran comes from jinns or devils). According to the dictionary, the term

jinn refers to an "unseen being created from fire". In Islam, jinns are divided into two categories: good and evil. The term devil refers to "a wicked spirit that tempts humans to commit evil deeds". In the context of the statement above, jinns are equated with devils, meaning the jinns referred to here are evil ones. Based on this explanation, it can be understood that the Quran is claimed to originate from a spirit or entity with evil characteristics. This implies that the Quran contains teachings of evil or negative elements. Furthermore, Luc xxx asserts that the Quran teaches misguidance, such as filth, murder, adultery, polygamy, and so on. This claim directly insults Islam and its holy scripture, portraying it in a derogatory and false manner. The third form of blasphemous speech against Islam can be seen in data 6-9. In data 6, a Facebook user named Sog xxx posted about interfaith relations, particularly between Islam and other religions. According to Sog xxx, Islam is hostile toward other religions such as Christianity, Hinduism, Buddhism, and indigenous beliefs, leading to conflicts. Meanwhile, Sog xxx claims that when other religions interact, they result in peace. For instance, Sog xxx mentions that Hinduism interacting with Buddhism, Hinduism with indigenous beliefs, Buddhism with indigenous beliefs, Christianity with Hinduism, Christianity with Buddhism, and Christianity with indigenous beliefs all lead to peace, which is the antonym of conflict.

Sog's post constitutes blasphemy against Islam. This is because it conveys a negative perception of Islam, portraying it as inherently antagonistic and prone to conflict with other religions. In other words, Islam is depicted as lacking tolerance toward other faiths. This statement is considered an inaccurate generalization, as not all Muslims exhibit antagonistic behavior toward other religions. Many individuals and groups within the Islamic faith respect diversity and coexist peacefully. Based on this analysis, it can be concluded that Sog xxx's statement perpetuates a negative stigma against Islam, misrepresenting its values and its adherents.

In data 7, a Facebook account under the name Sog xxx stated that majority-Muslim countries are always losing in various aspects. Economically, these countries are described as poor. In terms of warfare, they are claimed to always lose against their enemies. Politically, Sog xxx stated that majority-Muslim countries are often *dikadalin* (tricked), which means deceived or outsmarted. In the social aspect, they are considered *minder* (insecure), which according to the dictionary, means feeling inferior, incapable, or lacking self-confidence. Additionally, these countries are described as being easily influenced by the culture of other nations, suggesting that their cultural identity is not firmly rooted in the hearts of their people.

Sog xxx also claimed that the human resources (SDM) in majority-Muslim countries have low intelligence or are stupid. Overall, this post generalizes and demeans majority-Muslim countries by portraying them as failing in various aspects, including economics, politics, social issues, culture, and intelligence. This statement has the potential to incite hate speech that marginalizes Muslims.

Based on the analysis above, Sog xxx has committed an act of defamation against Islam. The statements were made without presenting data, evidence, or facts to substantiate the claim that majority-Muslim countries are failing in the aforementioned

aspects. In reality, there are approximately 50 countries in the world with a Muslim-majority population. Among these, each country has its own strengths and weaknesses, making it impossible to generalize them as all sharing the same flaws. Therefore, Soga's statements discredit Muslim-majority countries. This also implies an insult toward Islam as the religion practiced by the people in these countries, as though Islam is the cause of their alleged failures.

In data 8, a Facebook account named Y xxx discussed the differing opinions of three Islamic scholars (*ustad*) regarding a historical event significant to Christians, specifically about who was actually taken to Golgotha to be crucified. *Ustad Somad* mentioned Judas, a disciple of Jesus who betrayed him; *Ustad Waloni* referred to Barabbas, a rebel and thief known in Christian history; while *Ustad Kainama* referred to Yokohanan, one of Jesus's twelve apostles. This divergence of opinions became the basis for Y xxx to conclude that these *ustad* do not possess certainty regarding the crucifixion event. Y xxx then made a derogatory statement toward Islam by saying, *Islam raja ngibul* (Islam, king of lies).

The phrase *Islam raja ngibul* (Islam, king of lies) uses a metaphorical figure of speech, equating Islam with a king of deceit. According to the dictionary, Islam refers to the religion taught by the Prophet Muhammad; *raja* (king) means a supreme ruler or someone with particular prominence, while *ngibul* is a colloquial form of *pengibul*, which means a liar or deceiver. Using this figure of speech, Y xxx suggests that Islam is considered as being exceptionally skilled or superior in deceit. Based on this explanation, the meaning of the phrase *Islam, king of lies* implies that the religion taught by Prophet Muhammad is portrayed as having a unique characteristic of being a deceiver. Therefore, it is clear that Y's statement constitutes an insult or defamation of Islam by equating it with something (a person or teaching) adept in lying or deceiving.

In data 9, a Facebook account named Dun xxx posted a statement claiming that Islam adopted, altered, and falsified Christian teachings. This claim is explained in three clauses in the first sentence. The first clause states that Islam emerged 600 years after Christianity, implying that Christianity predates Islam. The second clause accuses Muslims (referred to as *kadrun*, a derogatory term derived from the phrase *kadal gurun* or "desert lizard") of stealing verses from the Bible to serve as arguments in the *Qur'an*. The third clause accuses Islam of falsifying the teachings of Jesus Christ and turning him into Prophet Isa.

This claim is further reinforced by the second sentence: *Si bungsu memang lucu sekali ya sampai Yesus pun mau di-Islamkan* (The youngest child is really funny, huh? Even Jesus is being 'Islamized'). In this sentence, the phrase *si bungsu* (the youngest child) refers to Islam as the last religion after Christianity. The phrase *lucu sekali* (really funny) in this context does not imply humor but rather serves to belittle Islam, suggesting that Islam attempts to Islamize Jesus by falsifying teachings.

Based on the explanation above, it can be said that the first sentence contains defamatory speech against Islam. This is evident from the use of the words *mencuri* (stole) and *memalsukannya* (falsified). According to the dictionary, *mencuri* (stole) is a verb that means "to take someone else's property without permission or illegally, usually in secret".

This verb carries a negative connotation, which in turn portrays the subject referred to by the verb, namely kadrun (in other words: muslims), in a negative or bad light. Similarly, the religion followed or believed by the subject, Islam, is also negatively portrayed. Additionally, the sentence contains the word *memalsukannya* (falsified), which grammatically means "to make something (in this case, Jesus Christ) fake or invalid". This statement defames Islam by claiming that there was falsification in the development of Islamic teachings regarding Jesus Christ, who is referred to in Islam as Prophet Isa.

4.2. Legal consequences of blasphemous speech against islam in Indonesia

Based on the forensic linguistic analysis above, it is strongly suspected that the nine statements made by netizens contain blasphemy against Islam. The legal basis for blasphemy in Indonesia refers to Article 156a of the Indonesian Criminal Code (KUHP), which states:

"Dipidana dengan pidana penjara selama-lamanya lima tahun barang siapa dengan sengaja di muka umum mengeluarkan perasaan atau melakukan perbuatan: (1) yang pada pokoknya bersifat permusuhan, penyalahgunaan atau penodaan terhadap suatu agama yang dianut di Indonesia; (2) dengan maksud agar supaya orang tidak menganut agama apapun juga, yang bersendikan Ketuhanan Yang Maha Esa".

(Anyone who deliberately, in public, expresses feelings or commits actions: (1) which are essentially hostile, abusive, or defamatory toward a religion adhered to in Indonesia; (2) with the intention of preventing others from adhering to any religion based on the belief in the Almighty God, shall be punished with a maximum imprisonment of five years). In addition, other articles related to offenses against religious life are regulated in Articles 175, 176, 177, and 503 of the Criminal Code.

Furthermore, the offense of religious defamation is also regulated under Law Number 1 of 2024, which is the second amendment to Law Number 11 of 2008 on Electronic Information and Transactions (ITE Law). The prohibition of religious blasphemy is stipulated in Article 28 paragraph (2) of the law, which states: "Setiap orang dengan sengaja dan tanpa hak menyebarkan informasi yang ditujukan untuk menimbulkan rasa kebencian atau permusuhan individu dan/atau kelompok masyarakat tertentu berdasarkan atas suku, agama, ras, dan antargolongan (SARA)". Adapun hukumannya diatur pada Pasal 45A ayat (2), yang berbunyi: "Setiap orang yang memenuhi unsur sebagaimana dimaksud dalam Pasal 28 ayat (2) dipidana dengan pidana penjara paling lama 6 (enam) tahun dan/atau denda paling banyak Rp1.000.000.000,00 (satu miliar rupiah)". (Any person who intentionally and without authority spreads information aimed at inciting hatred or hostility toward individuals and/or specific community groups based on ethnicity, religion, race, or inter-group affiliation (SARA)". The penalty is stipulated in Article 45A paragraph (2), which states: "Any person who fulfills the elements as referred to in Article 28 paragraph (2) shall be punished with a maximum imprisonment of six (6) years and/or a fine of up to IDR 1,000,000,000 (one billion rupiahs)).

Based on the explanation above, it can be concluded that the punishment for blasphemy under Indonesian law includes

imprisonment and/or fines. The maximum prison sentence is five or six years, while the maximum fine is one billion rupiahs.

5. CONCLUSION

In the digital era, social media platforms like Facebook serve as open spaces for interaction, including religious debates. However, the lack of linguistic awareness in the Islam versus Christianity debate group has led to the emergence of blasphemous speech. Analysis of nine netizen posts revealed statements that insult Islam, potentially violating Article 156a of the Criminal Code and Article 28(2) of Law Number 1 of 2024. Forensic linguistic analysis identified the nine blasphemous utterances against Islam above, and concluded that the pattern of blasphemy was (1) insulting God and Islamic symbols; (2) defamation of Islamic teachings and holy books; and (3) negative stereotypes of Islam as a religion and social identity. This study highlights the importance of applying forensic linguistics in analyzing linguistic crimes on social media, particularly in cases of religious blasphemy. Unlike previous studies, this research focuses on a religious debate group on Facebook, offering new insights into how blasphemous speech emerges in online interfaith discussions. The findings are expected to raise awareness among social media users to express their opinions more responsibly, especially on sensitive religious matters.

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